

FOURIER COEFFICIENTS OF A CLASS OF ETA QUOTIENTS

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Abstract

Recently, Williams, and then Yao, Xia and Jin, discovered explicit formulas for the coefficients of the Fourier series expansions of a class of eta quotients. Williams expressed all coefficients of one hundred and twenty-six eta quotients in terms of $\sigma(n)$, $\sigma(\frac{n}{2})$, $\sigma(\frac{n}{3})$ and $\sigma(\frac{n}{6})$, and Yao, Xia and Jin, following the method of Williams' proof, expressed only the even coefficients of one hundred and four eta quotients in terms of $\sigma_3(n)$, $\sigma_3(\frac{n}{2})$, $\sigma_3(\frac{n}{3})$ and $\sigma_3(\frac{n}{6})$. Here, by using the method of Williams' proof, we will express the odd Fourier coefficients of seventy-four eta quotients $f(q)$ in terms of $\sigma_5(2n-1)$ and $\sigma_5(\frac{2n-1}{3})$, i.e., the Fourier coefficients of the difference $f(q) - f(-q)$ of seventy-four eta quotients; and we will express the even Fourier coefficients of sixty eta quotients, i.e., the Fourier coefficients of the sum $f(q) + f(-q)$ of sixty eta quotients, in terms of $\sigma_5(n)$, $\sigma_5(\frac{n}{2})$, $\sigma_5(\frac{n}{3})$, $\sigma_5(\frac{n}{4})$, $\sigma_5(\frac{n}{6})$ and $\sigma_5(\frac{n}{12})$.

1. Introduction

The divisor function $\sigma_i(n)$ is defined for a positive integer i by

$$\sigma_i(n) = \begin{cases} \sum_{d \text{ positive integer}, d|n} d^i, & \text{if } n \text{ is a positive integer} \\ 0, & \text{if } n \text{ is not a positive integer} \end{cases}.$$

The Dedekind eta function is defined by

$$\eta(z) = q^{1/24} \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^n),$$

where

$$q = e^{2\pi iz}, z \in H = \{x + iy : y > 0\},$$

and an eta quotient of level n is defined by

$$f(z) = \prod_{m|n} \eta(mz)^{a_m}, n, m \in \mathbb{N}, a_m \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

It is interesting and important to find explicit formulas for the Fourier coefficients of eta quotients since they are the building blocks of modular forms of level n and weight k . The book of Koehler (see [13], p. 39) describes such expansions by means of Hecke theta series, and it develops algorithms for the determination of suitable eta quotients. One can find more information in [4, 6, 14, 18, 17]. Additionally, the present author has determined the Fourier coefficients of the theta series associated with some quadratic forms (see [12], [11], [10], [8], [7] and [9]).

Recently, Williams [16] discovered explicit formulas for the coefficients of the Fourier series expansions of a class of one hundred and twenty-six eta quotients in terms of $\sigma(n), \sigma(\frac{n}{2}), \sigma(\frac{n}{3})$ and $\sigma(\frac{n}{6})$. An example is

$$\frac{\eta^2(2z)\eta^4(4z)\eta^6(6z)}{\eta^2(z)\eta^2(3z)\eta^4(12z)} = 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} c(n)q^n,$$

where

$$c(n) = 2\sigma(n) - 3\sigma(n/2) + 4\sigma(n/4) + 9\sigma(n/6) - 36\sigma(n/12).$$

Then, Yao, Xia and Jin [15] expressed the even Fourier coefficients of one hundred and four eta quotients in terms of $\sigma_3(n), \sigma_3(\frac{n}{2}), \sigma_3(\frac{n}{3})$ and $\sigma_3(\frac{n}{6})$. One example is

$$\frac{\eta^{25}(2z)\eta^4(3z)}{\eta^{12}(z)\eta^5(4z)\eta^3(6z)\eta(12z)} = 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} c(n)q^n,$$

where

$$c(2n) = 65\sigma_3(n) - 68\sigma_3(n/2) - 81\sigma_3(n/3) + 324\sigma_3(n/6).$$

Motivated by these two results, we find that we can express the odd Fourier coefficients of seventy-four eta quotients in terms of $\sigma_5(2n + 1)$ and $\sigma_5(\frac{2n+1}{3})$; see Table1/A. An example is

$$\frac{\eta^{23}(4z)\eta^7(6z)}{\eta^{13}(2z)\eta^5(12z)} = 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} c(n)q^n,$$

where

$$c(2n - 1) = 0.$$

We can also express the even Fourier coefficients of sixty eta quotients in terms of $\sigma_5(n), \sigma_5(\frac{n}{2}), \sigma_5(\frac{n}{3}), \sigma_5(\frac{n}{4}), \sigma_5(\frac{n}{6})$ and $\sigma_5(\frac{n}{12})$; see Table2/A. An example is

$$\frac{\eta^{24}(2z)\eta^{12}(12z)}{\eta^{12}(4z)\eta^{12}(6z)} = 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} c(n)q^n,$$

where

$$c(2n) = 4\sigma_5(2n) - 132\sigma_5(n) + 128\sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) + 792\sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{3}\right).$$

Now we define some rational numbers and functions for the theorem: let $b_1, b_2, \dots, b_5$ be non-negative integers satisfying

$$b_1 + b_2 + \dots + b_5 \leq 12.$$

Define the integers a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_6 and a_{12} by

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 &= -b_1 + 2b_2 - 2b_3 - 4b_4 - b_5 + 12, \\ a_2 &= 3b_1 + b_2 + 3b_3 + 10b_4 + b_5 - 30, \\ a_3 &= 3b_1 + 2b_2 + 6b_3 + 4b_4 + 3b_5 - 36, \\ a_4 &= -2b_1 - b_2 - b_3 - 4b_4 + 2b_5 + 12, \\ a_6 &= -9b_1 - 7b_2 - 9b_3 - 10b_4 - 7b_5 + 90, \\ a_{12} &= 6b_1 + 3b_2 + 3b_3 + 4b_4 + 2b_5 - 36. \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Now define the integers $k_0, k_1, k_2, k_3, k_4, k_5, k_6, k_7, k_8, k_9, k_{10}, k_{11}$ and k_{12} by

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{2^{b_1+b_5}} x^{b_1} (1-x)^{b_2} (1+x)^{b_3} (1+2x)^{b_4} (2+x)^{b_5} = \\ &k_0 + k_1x + k_2x^2 + k_3x^3 + k_4x^4 + k_5x^5 + k_6x^6 \\ &+ k_7x^7 + k_8x^8 + k_9x^9 + k_{10}x^{10} + k_{11}x^{11} + k_{12}x^{12}. \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Let

$$\begin{aligned} f_1 &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_1(n) q^n = \eta(2z)\eta(4z)\eta^5(6z)\eta^5(12z), \\ f_2 &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_2(n) q^n = \eta^5(2z)\eta^5(4z)\eta(6z)\eta(12z), \\ f_3 &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_3(n) q^n = \frac{\eta^9(2z)\eta^9(12z)}{\eta^3(4z)\eta^3(6z)}, \\ f_4 &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_4(n) q^n = \frac{\eta^8(4z)\eta^{16}(6z)}{\eta^4(2z)\eta^8(12z)}, \\ f_5 &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_5(n) q^n = \eta^{12}(2z), \end{aligned}$$

$$f_6 = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_6(n) q^n = \frac{\eta^5(2z) \eta^{13}(6z)}{\eta(4z) \eta^5(12z)},$$

$$f_7 = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_7(n) q^n = \frac{\eta^{12}(4z) \eta^{24}(6z)}{\eta^{12}(2z) \eta^{12}(12z)}.$$

Now define integers $k_0, k_1, k_2, k_3, k_4, k_5, k_6, k_7, k_8, k_9, k_{10}, k_{11}$ and k_{12} by

$$\frac{1}{2^{b_1+b_5}} x^{b_1} (1-x)^{b_2} (1+x)^{b_3} (1+2x)^{b_4} (2+x)^{b_5}$$

$$= k_0 + k_1 x + k_2 x^2 + k_3 x^3 + k_4 x^4 + k_5 x^5 + k_6 x^6 + k_7 x^7 + k_8 x^8$$

$$+ k_9 x^9 + k_{10} x^{10} + k_{11} x^{11} + k_{12} x^{12}.$$

Define the rational numbers $c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, c_6, c_{12}, r_1, r_2, r_3, r_4, r_5, r_6$ and r_7 by

$$c_1 = \frac{20732}{8067} k_0 - \frac{45998}{24201} k_1 + \frac{32588}{24201} k_2 - \frac{2430}{2689} k_3$$

$$+ \frac{13684}{24201} k_4 - \frac{7774}{24201} k_5 + \frac{1252}{8067} k_6 - \frac{1118}{24201} k_7$$

$$- \frac{652}{24201} k_8 + \frac{518}{8067} k_9 - \frac{2456}{24201} k_{10} + \frac{2456}{24201} k_{11},$$

$$c_2 = -\frac{101678936}{734097} k_0 + \frac{65872684}{734097} k_1 - \frac{14225816}{244699} k_2$$

$$+ \frac{27033238}{734097} k_3 - \frac{2344028}{104871} k_4 + \frac{3081530}{244699} k_5$$

$$- \frac{4620236}{734097} k_6 + \frac{1635406}{734097} k_7 + \frac{102820}{244699} k_8$$

$$- \frac{1383458}{734097} k_9 + \frac{27016}{8067} k_{10} - \frac{934216}{244699} k_{11} + \frac{256}{273} k_{12},$$

$$c_3 = \frac{43804}{8067} k_0 - \frac{147610}{24201} k_1 + \frac{161020}{24201} k_2 - \frac{19082}{2689} k_3$$

$$+ \frac{179924}{24201} k_4 - \frac{185834}{24201} k_5 + \frac{63284}{8067} k_6 - \frac{192490}{24201} k_7$$

$$+ \frac{194260}{24201} k_8 - \frac{65054}{8067} k_9 + \frac{196064}{24201} k_{10} - \frac{196064}{24201} k_{11},$$

$$c_4 = \frac{99265280}{734097} k_0 - \frac{193319296}{2202291} k_1 + \frac{124840960}{2202291} k_2$$

$$- \frac{26219264}{734097} k_3 + \frac{6725120}{314613} k_4 - \frac{25219328}{2202291} k_5$$

$$+ \frac{1100544}{244699} k_6 + \frac{2423552}{2202291} k_7 - \frac{1178624}{169407} k_8$$

$$+ \frac{10973696}{734097} k_9 - \frac{9282304}{314613} k_{10} + \frac{123832960}{2202291} k_{11}$$

$$- \frac{28928}{273} k_{12},$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 c_6 = & \frac{89933384}{734097}k_0 - \frac{59999908}{734097}k_1 + \frac{12268224}{244699}k_2 \\
 & - \frac{21160462}{734097}k_3 + \frac{1505060}{104871}k_4 - \frac{1123938}{244699}k_5 \\
 & - \frac{1252540}{734097}k_6 + \frac{4237370}{734097}k_7 - \frac{2060412}{244699}k_8 \\
 & + \frac{7256234}{734097}k_9 - \frac{91552}{8067}k_{10} + \frac{2891808}{244699}k_{11} \\
 & + \frac{139520}{273}k_{12},
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 c_{12} = & \frac{276592384}{734097}k_0 + \frac{193319296}{2202291}k_1 - \frac{124840960}{2202291}k_2 \\
 & + \frac{26219264}{734097}k_3 - \frac{6725120}{314613}k_4 + \frac{25219328}{2202291}k_5 \\
 & - \frac{1100544}{244699}k_6 - \frac{2423552}{2202291}k_7 + \frac{1178624}{169407}k_8 \\
 & - \frac{10973696}{734097}k_9 + \frac{9282304}{314613}k_{10} - \frac{123832960}{2202291}k_{11} \\
 & - \frac{110848}{273}k_{12},
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 r_1 = & -\frac{608}{91}k_0 + \frac{26672}{91}k_1 - \frac{26480}{91}k_2 + \frac{19792}{91}k_3 \\
 & - \frac{1824}{13}k_4 + \frac{7680}{91}k_5 - \frac{4208}{91}k_6 + \frac{2032}{91}k_7 \\
 & - \frac{64}{7}k_8 - \frac{32}{91}k_9 + \frac{32}{13}k_{10} - \frac{608}{91}k_{11} + \frac{1216}{91}k_{12},
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 r_2 = & \frac{8272}{273}k_0 + \frac{456}{91}k_1 - \frac{2648}{273}k_2 + \frac{1912}{273}k_3 \\
 & - \frac{48}{13}k_4 + \frac{544}{273}k_5 - \frac{320}{273}k_6 + \frac{64}{91}k_7 \\
 & - \frac{128}{273}k_8 + \frac{64}{273}k_9 - \frac{128}{273}k_{11} + \frac{256}{273}k_{12},
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 r_3 = & \frac{144}{13}k_0 - \frac{1624}{39}k_1 + 40k_2 - \frac{392}{13}k_3 + \frac{752}{39}k_4 \\
 & - \frac{128}{13}k_5 + \frac{16}{13}k_6 + \frac{272}{39}k_7 - \frac{192}{13}k_8 \\
 & + \frac{288}{13}k_9 - \frac{1120}{39}k_{10} + \frac{544}{13}k_{11} - \frac{1088}{13}k_{12},
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 r_4 = & -\frac{149764}{2689}k_0 + \frac{428678}{8067}k_1 - \frac{361214}{8067}k_2 + \frac{90816}{2689}k_3 \\
 & - \frac{183448}{8067}k_4 + \frac{108562}{8067}k_5 - \frac{17726}{2689}k_6 + \frac{13724}{8067}k_7 \\
 & + \frac{13372}{8067}k_8 - \frac{9370}{2689}k_9 + \frac{42848}{8067}k_{10} - \frac{42848}{8067}k_{11},
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 r_5 &= \frac{38036}{8067}k_0 - \frac{98006}{24201}k_1 + \frac{80510}{24201}k_2 - \frac{6852}{2689}k_3 \\
 &\quad + \frac{41560}{24201}k_4 - \frac{20314}{24201}k_5 - \frac{626}{8067}k_6 + \frac{24760}{24201}k_7 \\
 &\quad - \frac{48076}{24201}k_8 + \frac{23942}{8067}k_9 - \frac{95576}{24201}k_{10} + \frac{95576}{24201}k_{11}, \\
 r_6 &= -\frac{136}{2689}k_0 + \frac{364}{8067}k_1 - \frac{220}{8067}k_2 - \frac{30}{2689}k_3 \\
 &\quad + \frac{676}{8067}k_4 - \frac{1714}{8067}k_5 + \frac{1156}{2689}k_6 - \frac{6290}{8067} \\
 &\quad k_7 + \frac{10532}{8067}k_8 - \frac{5398}{2689}k_9 + \frac{21856}{8067}k_{10} - \frac{21856}{8067}k_{11}, \\
 r_7 &= \frac{111864}{2689}k_0 - \frac{395572}{8067}k_1 + \frac{345460}{8067}k_2 - \frac{86364}{2689}k_3 \\
 &\quad + \frac{173480}{8067}k_4 - \frac{102668}{8067}k_5 + \frac{17196}{2689}k_6 - \frac{16060}{8067}k_7 \\
 &\quad - \frac{8096}{8067}k_8 + \frac{6960}{2689}k_9 - \frac{33664}{8067}k_{10} + \frac{33664}{8067}k_{11}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now we can state our main theorem:

Theorem 1. *The functions $f_1, f_2, \dots, f_6$ are in $S_6(\Gamma_0(12))$, while f_7 is in $M_6(\Gamma_0(12))$, and*

$$\eta^{a_1}(z)\eta^{a_2}(2z)\eta^{a_3}(3z)\eta^{a_4}(4z)\eta^{a_6}(6z)\eta^{a_{12}}(12z) = \delta(b_1) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} c(n)q^n,$$

where for $n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 c(n) &= -c_1\sigma_5(n) - c_2\sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) - c_3\sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{3}\right) - c_4\sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{4}\right) - c_6\sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{6}\right) - c_{12}\sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{12}\right) \\
 &\quad + r_1f_1(n) + r_2f_2(n) + r_3f_3(n) + r_4f_4(n) + r_5f_5(n) + r_6f_6(n) + r_7f_7(n).
 \end{aligned}$$

In particular,

$$\begin{aligned}
 c(2n) &= -c_1\sigma_5(2n) - c_2\sigma_5(n) - c_4\sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) - (33c_3 + c_6)\sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{3}\right) \\
 &\quad - (c_{12} - 32c_3)\sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{6}\right) + r_1f_1(2n) + r_2f_2(2n) + r_3f_3(2n), \\
 c(2n-1) &= -c_1\sigma_5(2n-1) - c_3\sigma_5\left(\frac{2n-1}{3}\right) \\
 &\quad + r_4f_4(2n-1) + r_5f_5(2n-1) + r_6f_6(2n-1) + r_7f_7(2n-1),
 \end{aligned}$$

for $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Proof. It follows from (1) that

$$a_1 + 2a_2 + 3a_3 + 4a_4 + 6a_6 + 12a_{12} = 24b_1,$$

$$a_1 + a_2 + a_3 + a_4 + a_6 + a_{12} = 12$$

and

$$-\frac{a_1}{6} - \frac{a_2}{3} - \frac{a_3}{6} - 2\frac{a_4}{3} - \frac{a_6}{3} - 2\frac{a_{12}}{3} = -b_1 - b_5.$$

Now we will use (p, k) , the parametrization of Alaca, Alaca and Williams (see [2]):

$$p(q) = \frac{\varphi^2(q) - \varphi^2(q^3)}{2\varphi^2(q^3)}, k(q) = \frac{\varphi^3(q^3)}{\varphi(q)},$$

where the theta function $\varphi(q)$ is defined by

$$\varphi(q) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} q^{n^2}.$$

Setting $x = p$ in (2) and multiplying both sides by k^6 , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{k^6}{2^{b_1+b_5}} p^{b_1} (1-p)^{b_2} (1+p)^{b_3} (1+2p)^{b_4} (2+p)^{b_5} \\ = (k_0 + k_1p + k_2p^2 + k_3p^3 + k_4p^4 + k_5p^5 + k_6p^6 \\ + k_7p^7 + k_8p^8 + k_9p^9 + k_{10}p^{10} + k_{11}p^{11} + k_{12}p^{12})k^6. \end{aligned}$$

Alaca, Alaca and Williams [1] have established the following representations in terms of p and k :

$$\eta(q) = 2^{-1/6} p^{1/24} (1-p)^{1/2} (1+p)^{1/6} (1+2p)^{1/8} (2+p)^{1/8} k^{1/2}, \tag{3}$$

$$\eta(q^2) = 2^{-1/3} p^{1/12} (1-p)^{1/4} (1+p)^{1/12} (1+2p)^{1/4} (2+p)^{1/4} k^{1/2}, \tag{4}$$

$$\eta(q^3) = 2^{-1/6} p^{1/8} (1-p)^{1/6} (1+p)^{1/2} (1+2p)^{1/24} (2+p)^{1/24} k^{1/2}, \tag{5}$$

$$\eta(q^4) = 2^{-2/3} p^{1/6} (1-p)^{1/8} (1+p)^{1/24} (1+2p)^{1/8} (2+p)^{1/2} k^{1/2}, \tag{6}$$

$$\eta(q^6) = 2^{-1/3} p^{1/4} (1-p)^{1/12} (1+p)^{1/4} (1+2p)^{1/12} (2+p)^{1/12} k^{1/2}, \tag{7}$$

$$\eta(q^{12}) = 2^{-2/3} p^{1/2} (1-p)^{1/24} (1+p)^{1/8} (1+2p)^{1/24} (2+p)^{1/6} k^{1/2}. \tag{8}$$

We also have the following:

$$\begin{aligned} E_6(q) = 1 - 504 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sigma_5(n) q^n &= (1 - 246p - 5532p^2 - 38614p^3 - 135369p^4 - 276084p^5 \\ &\quad - 348024p^6 - 276084p^7 - 135369p^8 - 38614p^9 - 5532p^{10} \\ &\quad - 246p^{11} + p^{12})k^6, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_6(q^2) &= (1 + 6p - 114p^2 - 625p^3 - \frac{4059}{2}p^4 - 4302p^5 \\
 &\quad - 5556p^6 - 4302p^7 - \frac{4059}{2}p^8 - 625p^9 - 114p^{10} \\
 &\quad + 6p^{11} + p^{12})k^6, \\
 E_6(q^3) &= (1 + 6p + 12p^2 - 58p^3 - 297p^4 - 396p^5 - 264p^6 - 396p^7 \\
 &\quad - 297p^8 - 58p^9 + 12p^{10} + 6p^{11} + p^{12})k^6, \\
 E_6(q^4) &= (1 + 6p + 12p^2 + 5p^3 - 45p^4 - 144p^5 - \frac{1167}{8}p^6 + \frac{171}{8}p^7 \\
 &\quad + \frac{2151}{32}p^8 - \frac{739}{16}p^9 - \frac{345}{8}p^{10} \\
 &\quad + \frac{129}{32}p^{11} + \frac{1}{64}p^{12})k^6, \\
 E_6(q^6) &= (1 + 6p + 12p^2 + 5p^3 - \frac{27}{2}p^4 - 18p^5 \\
 &\quad - 12p^6 - 18p^7 - \frac{27}{2}p^8 + 5p^9 + 12p^{10} + 6p^{11} + p^{12})k^6, \\
 E_6(q^{12}) &= (1 + 6p + 12p^2 + 5p^3 - \frac{27}{2}p^4 - 18p^5 \\
 &\quad - \frac{33}{8}p^6 + \frac{45}{8}p^7 + \frac{135}{32}p^8 + \frac{17}{16}p^9 + \frac{3}{16}p^{10} \\
 &\quad + \frac{3}{32}p^{11} + \frac{1}{64}p^{12})k^6.
 \end{aligned}$$

It is easy to check the following expressions using (3)-(8):

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_1 &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_1(n) q^n = \eta(2z) \eta(4z) \eta^5(6z) \eta^5(12z) \\
 &= \left(\frac{1}{16}p^4 + \frac{1}{4}p^5 + \frac{17}{64}p^6 - \frac{5}{64}p^7 - \frac{19}{64}p^8 - \frac{11}{64}p^9 - \frac{1}{32}p^{10} \right) k^6, \\
 f_2 &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_2(n) q^n = \eta^5(2z) \eta^5(4z) \eta(6z) \eta(12z) \\
 &= \left(\frac{1}{4}p^2 + \frac{5}{4}p^3 + \frac{13}{8}p^4 - p^5 - \frac{223}{64}p^6 - \frac{109}{64}p^7 \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{71}{64}p^8 + \frac{89}{64}p^9 + \frac{1}{2}p^{10} + \frac{1}{16}p^{11} \right) k^6, \\
 f_3 &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_3(n) q^n = \frac{\eta^9(2z) \eta^9(12z)}{\eta^3(4z) \eta^3(6z)} \\
 &= \left(\frac{1}{16}p^4 + \frac{1}{4}p^5 + \frac{9}{64}p^6 - \frac{29}{64}p^7 \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \frac{29}{64}p^8 + \frac{9}{64}p^9 + \frac{1}{4}p^{10} + \frac{1}{16}p^{11} \right) k^6,
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_4 &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_4(n) q^n = \frac{\eta^8(4z)\eta^{16}(6z)}{\eta^4(2z)\eta^8(12z)} \\
 &= \left(\frac{1}{2}p + \frac{11}{4}p^2 + \frac{43}{8}p^3 + \frac{57}{16}p^4 - \frac{9}{4}p^5 \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \frac{21}{4}p^6 - \frac{7}{2}p^7 - \frac{17}{16}p^8 - \frac{1}{8}p^9\right)k^6, \\
 f_5 &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_5(n) q^n = \eta^{12}(2z) \\
 &= \left(\frac{1}{2}p + \frac{11}{4}p^2 + \frac{27}{8}p^3 - \frac{87}{16}p^4 - \frac{51}{4}p^5 \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{51}{4}p^7 + \frac{87}{16}p^8 - \frac{27}{8}p^9 - \frac{11}{4}p^{10} - \frac{1}{2}p^{11}\right)k^6, \\
 f_6 &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_6(n) q^n = \frac{\eta^5(2z)\eta^{13}(6z)}{\eta(4z)\eta^5(12z)} \\
 &= \left(\frac{1}{2}p + \frac{11}{4}p^2 + \frac{17}{4}p^3 - \frac{3}{2}p^4 - 9p^5 \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \frac{21}{4}p^6 + \frac{13}{4}p^7 + 4p^8 + p^9\right)k^6, \\
 f_7 &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_7(n) q^n = \frac{\eta^{12}(4z)\eta^{24}(6z)}{\eta^{12}(2z)\eta^{12}(12z)} \\
 &= \left(\frac{1}{2}p + \frac{11}{4}p^2 + \frac{51}{8}p^3 + \frac{129}{16}p^4 + 6p^5 \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{21}{8}p^6 + \frac{5}{8}p^7 + \frac{1}{16}p^8\right)k^6.
 \end{aligned}$$

We see that $f_1, \dots, f_6, \in S_6(\Gamma_0(12))$, $f_7 \in M_6(\Gamma_0(12))$ and

$$ord_{1/1}f_7 = 0, \quad ord_{1/2}f_7 = 0,$$

by [5]. Now

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\eta^{a_1}(z)\eta^{a_2}(2z)\eta^{a_3}(3z)\eta^{a_4}(4z)\eta^{a_6}(6z)\eta^{a_{12}}(12z) \\
 &= q^{b_1} \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^n)^{a_1} (1 - q^{2n})^{a_2} (1 - q^{3n})^{a_3} (1 - q^{4n})^{a_4} (1 - q^{6n})^{a_6} (1 - q^{12n})^{a_{12}} \\
 &= 2^{-\frac{a_1}{6} - \frac{a_2}{3} - \frac{a_3}{6} - 2\frac{a_4}{3} - \frac{a_6}{3} - 2\frac{a_{12}}{3}} p^{\frac{a_1}{24} + \frac{a_2}{12} + \frac{a_3}{8} + \frac{a_4}{6} + \frac{a_6}{4} + \frac{a_{12}}{2}} (1 - p)^{\frac{a_1}{2} + \frac{a_2}{4} + \frac{a_3}{6} + \frac{a_4}{8} + \frac{a_6}{12} + \frac{a_{12}}{24}} \\
 &\quad (1 + p)^{\frac{a_1}{6} + \frac{a_2}{12} + \frac{a_3}{2} + \frac{a_4}{24} + \frac{a_6}{4} + \frac{a_{12}}{8}} (1 + 2p)^{\frac{a_1}{8} + \frac{a_2}{4} + \frac{a_3}{24} + \frac{a_4}{8} + \frac{a_6}{12} + \frac{a_{12}}{24}} (2 + p)^{\frac{a_1}{8} + \frac{a_2}{4} + \frac{a_3}{24} + \frac{a_4}{2} + \frac{a_6}{12} + \frac{a_{12}}{6}} \\
 &k^{\frac{a_1 + a_2 + a_3 + a_4 + a_6 + a_{12}}{2}} = \frac{k^6}{2^{b_1 + b_5}} p^{b_1} (1 - p)^{b_2} (1 + p)^{b_3} (1 + 2p)^{b_4} (2 + p)^{b_5}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= k^6(k_0 + k_1p + k_2p^2 + k_3p^3 + k_4p^4 + k_5p^5 + k_6p^6 \\
 &\quad + k_7p^7 + k_8p^8 + k_9p^9 + k_{10}p^{10} + k_{11}p^{11} + k_{12}p^{12}) \\
 &= \frac{c_1}{504} \left(1 - 504 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sigma_5(n) q^n\right) + \frac{c_2}{504} \left(1 - 504 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sigma_5(n) q^{2n}\right) \\
 &\quad + \frac{c_3}{504} \left(1 - 504 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sigma_5(n) q^{3n}\right) + \frac{c_4}{504} \left(1 - 504 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sigma_5(n) q^{4n}\right) \\
 &\quad + \frac{c_6}{504} \left(1 - 504 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sigma_5(n) q^{6n}\right) + \frac{c_{12}}{504} \left(1 - 504 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sigma_5(n) q^{12n}\right) \\
 &\quad + r_1 q^4 \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{2n}) (1 - q^{4n}) (1 - q^{6n})^5 (1 - q^{12n})^5 \\
 &\quad + r_2 q^2 \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{2n})^5 (1 - q^{4n})^5 (1 - q^{6n}) (1 - q^{12n}) \\
 &\quad + r_3 q^4 \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1 - q^{2n})^9 (1 - q^{12n})^9}{(1 - q^{4n})^3 (1 - q^{6n})^3} \\
 &\quad + r_4 q \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1 - q^{4n})^8 (1 - q^{6n})^{16}}{(1 - q^{2n})^4 (1 - q^{12n})^8} \\
 &\quad + r_5 \cdot q \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{2n})^{12} + r_6 q \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1 - q^{2n})^5 (1 - q^{6n})^{13}}{(1 - q^{4n}) (1 - q^{12n})^5} \\
 &\quad + r_7 q \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1 - q^{4n})^{12} (1 - q^{6n})^{24}}{(1 - q^{2n})^{12} (1 - q^{12n})^{12}} \\
 &= \delta(b_1) - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (c_1 \sigma_5(n) + c_2 \sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) + c_3 \sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{3}\right) + c_4 \sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{4}\right) \\
 &\quad + c_6 \sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{6}\right) + c_{12} \sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{12}\right)) q^n + r_1 f_1(n) q^n + \dots + r_7 f_7(n) q^n,
 \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\delta(b_1) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } b_1 \neq 0 \\ 1 & \text{if } b_1 = 0 \end{cases} .$$

So

$$\begin{aligned}
 c(n) &= -(c_1 \sigma_5(n) + c_2 \sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) + c_3 \sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{3}\right) + c_4 \sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{4}\right) \\
 &\quad + c_6 \sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{6}\right) + c_{12} \sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{12}\right)) + r_1 f_1(n) + \dots + r_7 f_7(n).
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, for $n = 1, 2, \dots$,

$$c(2n) = -c_1\sigma_5(2n) - c_2\sigma_5(n) - c_4\sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) - (33c_3 + c_6)\sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{3}\right) - (c_{12} - 32c_3)\sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{6}\right) + r_1f_1(2n) + r_2f_2(2n) + r_3f_3(2n),$$

$$c(2n - 1) = -c_1\sigma_5(2n - 1) - c_3\sigma_5\left(\frac{2n - 1}{3}\right) + r_4f_4(2n - 1) + r_5f_5(2n - 1) + r_6f_6(2n - 1) + r_7f_7(2n - 1),$$

since it is easy to see that

$$\sigma_5\left(\frac{2n}{3}\right) = 33\sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{3}\right) - 32\sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{6}\right),$$

and, for $n = 1, 2, \dots$,

$$f_1(2n - 1) = f_2(2n - 1) = f_3(2n - 1) = 0,$$

$$f_4(2n) = f_5(2n) = f_6(2n) = f_7(2n) = 0.$$

These formulas are valid for 6135 nontrivial eta quotients; see www.bariskendirli.com.tr/eta_quotients.

Among them, we have found 74 eta quotients (see Table1/A), such that

$$c(2n) = -c_1\sigma_5(2n) - c_2\sigma_5(n) - c_4\sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) - (33c_3 + c_6)\sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{3}\right) - (c_{12} - 32c_3)\sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{6}\right) + r_1f_1(2n) + r_2f_2(2n) + r_3f_3(2n),$$

$$c(2n - 1) = -c_1\sigma_5(2n - 1) - c_3\sigma_5\left(\frac{2n - 1}{3}\right) = 0;$$

and 60 eta quotients (see Table2/A), such that

$$c(2n) = -c_1\sigma_5(2n) - c_2\sigma_5(n) - c_4\sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) - (33c_3 + c_6)\sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{3}\right) - (c_{12} - 32c_3)\sigma_5\left(\frac{n}{6}\right),$$

$$c(2n - 1) = -c_1\sigma_5(2n - 1) - c_3\sigma_5\left(\frac{2n - 1}{3}\right) + r_4f_4(2n - 1) + r_5f_5(2n - 1) + r_6f_6(2n - 1) + r_7f_7(2n - 1).$$

Remark 1: The coefficients $k_0, k_1, k_2, k_3, k_4, k_5, k_6, k_7, k_8, k_9, k_{10}, k_{11}, k_{12}$ and $r_1, r_2, r_3, r_4, r_5, r_6, r_7$ are given in Table1/B and Table2/B.

Remark 2: If f is an eta quotient, then $f(-q)$ is also an eta quotient, the coefficients of $\frac{1}{2}(f(q) - f(-q))$ are exactly the odd coefficients of f , and the coefficients of $\frac{1}{2}(f(q) + f(-q))$ are exactly the even coefficients of f . In particular, this means that we have obtained all coefficients of the difference of seventy-four eta quotients and the sum of sixty eta quotients.

Remark 3: The space $S_6(\Gamma_0(12))$ is seven-dimensional(see [3, Chapter 3 and 5]), and it is generated by

$$\Delta_{3,6}, \Delta_{3,6}(2z), \Delta_{3,6}(4z), \Delta_{4,6}, \Delta_{4,6}(3z), \Delta_{6,6}, \Delta_{6,6}(2z),$$

where $\Delta_{3,6}$ is the unique newform in $S_6(\Gamma_0(3))$, $\Delta_{4,6}$ is the unique newform in $S_6(\Gamma_0(4))$, and $\Delta_{6,6}$ is the unique newform in $S_6(\Gamma_0(6))$. By simple calculation, we see that

$$\begin{aligned} f_1 &= -\frac{1}{18}\Delta_{3,6}(2z) + \frac{4}{9}\Delta_{3,6}(4z) + \frac{1}{18}\Delta_{6,6}(2z), \\ f_2 &= \frac{1}{2}\Delta_{3,6}(2z) - 4\Delta_{3,6}(4z) + \frac{1}{2}\Delta_{6,6}(2z), \\ f_3 &= -\frac{1}{2}\Delta_{3,6}(2z) - 4\Delta_{3,6}(4z) + \frac{1}{2}\Delta_{6,6}(2z), \\ f_4 &= \frac{4}{9}\Delta_{3,6}(z) + \frac{8}{3}\Delta_{3,6}(2z) + \frac{128}{9}\Delta_{3,6}(4z) + \frac{1}{3}\Delta_{4,6}(z) \\ &\quad + 6\Delta_{4,6}(2z) + \frac{2}{9}\Delta_{6,6}(z) - \frac{8}{9}\Delta_{6,6}(2z), \\ f_5 &= \Delta_{4,6}(z), \\ f_6 &= \frac{4}{9}\Delta_{3,6}(z) + \frac{8}{3}\Delta_{3,6}(2z) + \frac{128}{9}\Delta_{3,6}(4z) + \frac{1}{3}\Delta_{4,6}(z) \\ &\quad - 3\Delta_{4,6}(2z) + \frac{2}{9}\Delta_{6,6}(z) - \frac{8}{9}\Delta_{6,6}(2z). \end{aligned}$$

Note that f_7 is in $M_6(\Gamma_0(12)) \setminus S_6(\Gamma_0(12))$, so it can be written in the form

$$\begin{aligned} f_7 &= \frac{55}{117}\Delta_{3,6}(z) + \frac{110}{39}\Delta_{3,6}(2z) + \frac{1760}{117}\Delta_{3,6}(4z) + \frac{1}{3}\Delta_{4,6}(z) + 8\Delta_{4,6}(2z) \\ &\quad + \frac{11}{63}\Delta_{6,6}(z) - \frac{44}{63}\Delta_{6,6}(2z) - \frac{1}{22932}E_6(z) + \frac{11}{7644}E_6(2z) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{22932}E_6(3z) - \frac{8}{5733}E_6(4z) - \frac{11}{7644}E_6(6z) + \frac{8}{5733}E_6(12z). \end{aligned}$$

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Appendix

Table 1/A

<i>No</i>	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_6	a_{12}	c_2	c_4	c_6	c_{12}
1	0	-18	0	36	6	-12	-4905/1456	3897/1456	-6561/1456	741393/1456
2	0	-17	0	31	11	-13	-2179/728	1675/728	-3645/728	371061/728
3	0	-16	0	26	16	-14	-242/91	179/91	-486/91	46413/91
4	0	-15	0	21	21	-15	-215/91	152/91	-513/91	46440/91
5	0	-14	0	16	26	-16	-191/91	128/91	-537/91	46464/91
6	0	-13	0	11	31	-17	-509/273	320/273	-1675/273	139456/273
7	0	-12	0	6	36	-18	-452/273	256/273	-1732/273	139520/273
8	0	-9	0	27	3	-9	9/728	-513/728	-6561/728	373977/728
9	0	-8	0	22	8	-10	1/91	-64/61	-729/91	46656/91
10	0	-7	0	17	13	-11	1/91	-64/91	-729/91	46656/91
11	0	-6	0	12	18	-12	1/91	-64/91	-729/91	46656/91
12	0	-5	0	7	23	-13	1/91	-64/91	-729/91	46656/91
13	0	-4	0	2	28	-14	4/273	-256/273	-2188/273	140032/273
14	0	0	0	18	0	-6	0	-9/13	0	6561/13
15	0	1	0	13	5	-7	1/91	-64/91	-729/91	46656/91
16	0	2	0	8	10	-8	1/91	-64/91	-729/91	46656/91
17	0	3	0	3	15	-9	1/91	-64/91	-729/91	46656/91
18	0	4	0	-2	20	-10	4/91	-256/91	-732/91	46848/91
19	0	9	0	9	-3	-3	9/91	-72/91	-6561/91	52488/91
20	0	10	0	4	2	-4	1/91	-64/91	-729/91	46656/91
21	0	11	0	-1	7	-5	1/91	-64/91	-729/91	46656/91
22	0	12	0	-6	12	-6	4/13	-256/13	-108/13	6912/13
23	0	18	0	0	-6	0	-9/13	0	6561/13	0
24	0	19	0	-5	-1	-1	1/91	-64/91	-729/91	46656/91
25	0	20	0	-10	4	-2	244/91	-15616/91	-972/91	62208/91
26	0	27	0	-9	-9	3	513/91	-576/91	-373977/91	419904/91
27	0	28	0	-14	-4	2	2188/91	-140032/91	-2916/91	186624/91
28	0	36	0	-18	-12	6	15588/91	-1255680/91	2965572/91	-1679616/91
29	0	-14	0	28	2	-4	-547/1456	547/1456	729/1456	-729/1456
30	0	-13	0	23	7	-5	-243/728	243/728	243/728	-243/728
31	0	-12	0	18	12	-6	-27/91	27/91	27/91	-27/91
32	0	-11	0	13	17	-7	-24/91	24/91	24/91	-24/91
33	0	-10	0	8	22	-8	-64/273	64/273	64/273	-64/273
34	0	-9	0	3	27	-9	-19/91	64/273	19/91	-64/273
35	0	-5	0	19	-1	-1	1/728	-1/728	-729/728	729/728
36	0	-1	0	-1	19	-5	-1/273	64/273	1/273	-64/273
37	0	4	0	10	-4	2	-1/91	1/91	729/91	-729/91
38	0	7	0	-5	11	-1	-3/91	192/91	3/91	-192/91
39	0	13	0	1	-7	5	8/91	-8/91	-5832/91	5832/91
40	0	15	0	-9	3	3	-27/91	1728/91	27/91	-1728/91
41	0	22	0	-8	-10	8	-64/91	64/91	46656/91	-46656/91
42	0	23	0	-13	-5	7	-243/91	15552/91	243/91	-15552/91
43	0	31	0	-17	-13	11	-1675/91	139456/91	-371061/91	233280/91

44	0	-10	0	20	-2	4	-61/1456	61/1456	243/1456	-243/1456
45	0	-9	0	15	3	3	-27/728	27/728	27/728	-27/728
46	0	-8	0	10	8	2	-3/91	3/91	3/91	-3/910
47	0	-7	0	5	13	1	-8/273	8/273	8/273	-8/273
48	0	-6	0	0	18	0	-1/39	0	1/39	0
49	0	-1	0	11	-5	7	1/728	-1/728	-729/728	729/728
50	0	2	0	-4	10	4	1/273	-64/273	-1/273	64/273
51	0	8	0	2	-8	10	-1/91	1/91	729/91	-729/91
52	0	10	0	-8	2	8	3/91	-192/91	-3/91	192/91
53	0	17	0	-7	-11	13	8/91	-8/91	-5832/91	5832/91
54	0	18	0	-12	-6	12	27/91	-1728/91	-27/91	1728/91
55	0	26	0	-16	-14	16	179/91	-15488/91	46413/91	-31104/91
56	0	-6	0	12	-6	12	-1/208	1/208	27/208	-27/208
57	0	-5	0	7	-1	11	-3/728	3/728	3/728	-3/728
58	0	-4	0	2	4	10	-1/273	1/273	1/273	-1/273
59	0	-3	0	-3	9	9	-1/273	8/273	1/273	-8/273
60	0	3	0	3	-9	15	1/728	-1/728	-729/728	729/728
61	0	5	0	-7	1	13	-1/273	64/273	1/273	-64/273
62	0	12	0	-6	-12	18	-1/91	1/91	729/91	-729/91
63	0	13	0	-11	-7	17	-3/91	192/91	3/91	-192/91
64	0	21	0	-15	-15	21	-19/91	1720/91	-5805/91	4104/91
65	0	-2	0	4	-10	20	-1/1456	1/1456	183/1456	-183/1456
66	0	-1	0	-1	-5	19	-1/2184	1/2184	1/2184	-1/2184
67	0	0	0	-6	0	18	0	-1/39	0	1/39
68	0	7	0	-5	-13	23	1/728	-1/728	-729/728	729/728
69	0	8	0	-10	-8	22	1/273	-64/273	-1/273	64/273
70	0	16	0	-14	-16	26	2/91	-191/91	726/91	-537/91
71	0	2	0	-4	-14	28	-1/4368	1/4368	547/4368	-547/4368
72	0	3	0	-9	-9	27	-1/2184	19/728	1/2184	-19/728
73	0	11	0	-13	-17	31	-5/2184	509/2184	-2179/2184	1675/2184
74	0	6	0	-12	-18	36	1/4368	-113/4368	545/4368	-433/4368

Table 1/B

No	k_0	k_1	k_2	k_3	k_4	k_5	k_6	k_7	k_8	k_9	k_{10}	k_{11}	k_{12}	r_1	r_2	r_3	
1	1	6	$\frac{33}{2}$	$\frac{55}{2}$	$\frac{495}{16}$	$\frac{99}{4}$	$\frac{231}{16}$	$\frac{99}{16}$	$\frac{495}{256}$	$\frac{55}{128}$	$\frac{33}{21}$	$\frac{3}{512}$	$\frac{1}{4096}$	772011	21303	12393	
2	1	6	$\frac{65}{4}$	$\frac{105}{4}$	$\frac{225}{8}$	21	$\frac{32}{357}$	$\frac{16}{135}$	$\frac{32}{286}$	$\frac{25}{23}$	$\frac{21}{1024}$	$\frac{3}{1024}$	0	$\frac{5824}{23085}$	$\frac{1456}{10137}$	$\frac{832}{1485}$	
3	1	6	16	25	$\frac{203}{8}$	$\frac{35}{2}$	$\frac{32}{133}$	$\frac{32}{43}$	$\frac{256}{145}$	$\frac{128}{9}$	$\frac{1}{256}$	$\frac{1}{1024}$	0	$\frac{182}{87723}$	$\frac{728}{1214}$	$\frac{104}{1413}$	
4	1	6	$\frac{63}{4}$	$\frac{95}{4}$	$\frac{363}{16}$	$\frac{57}{2}$	$\frac{16}{377}$	$\frac{16}{99}$	$\frac{256}{15}$	$\frac{128}{1}$	0	0	0	$\frac{728}{10350}$	$\frac{91}{1150}$	$\frac{104}{167}$	
5	1	6	$\frac{31}{2}$	$\frac{45}{2}$	$\frac{321}{16}$	$\frac{45}{4}$	$\frac{64}{31}$	$\frac{64}{3}$	$\frac{64}{1}$	$\frac{1}{64}$	0	0	0	$\frac{91}{9712}$	$\frac{91}{1083}$	$\frac{13}{157}$	
6	1	6	$\frac{61}{4}$	$\frac{85}{4}$	$\frac{16}{35}$	$\frac{4}{2}$	$\frac{8}{17}$	$\frac{4}{2}$	$\frac{16}{9}$	0	0	0	0	$\frac{91}{9064}$	$\frac{91}{3040}$	$\frac{13}{440}$	
7	1	6	15	20	15	6	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{91}{8416}$	$\frac{273}{2524}$	$\frac{39}{136}$	
8	1	6	$\frac{57}{4}$	$\frac{65}{4}$	$\frac{45}{8}$	-9	$-\frac{483}{32}$	$-\frac{369}{32}$	$-\frac{1395}{256}$	$-\frac{215}{128}$	$-\frac{339}{1024}$	$-\frac{39}{1024}$	$-\frac{1}{512}$	59049	6561	243	
9	1	6	14	15	$\frac{27}{8}$	$-\frac{21}{2}$	$-\frac{231}{16}$	$-\frac{32}{153}$	$-\frac{975}{256}$	$-\frac{119}{119}$	$-\frac{33}{33}$	$-\frac{1}{128}$	0	$\frac{728}{50787}$	$\frac{728}{729}$	$\frac{26}{837}$	
10	1	6	$\frac{55}{4}$	$\frac{55}{4}$	$\frac{19}{16}$	$-\frac{47}{4}$	$-\frac{863}{64}$	$-\frac{485}{64}$	$-\frac{155}{27}$	$-\frac{27}{64}$	$-\frac{1}{32}$	0	0	$\frac{5427}{91}$	$\frac{638}{91}$	$\frac{90}{91}$	
11	1	6	$\frac{27}{2}$	$\frac{25}{2}$	$-\frac{15}{16}$	$-\frac{51}{4}$	$-\frac{49}{4}$	$-\frac{45}{8}$	$-\frac{21}{16}$	$-\frac{1}{8}$	0	0	0	4608	547	77	
12	1	6	$\frac{53}{4}$	$\frac{45}{4}$	-3	$-\frac{27}{2}$	$-\frac{43}{4}$	$-\frac{15}{4}$	$-\frac{1}{2}$	0	0	0	0	$\frac{91}{3880}$	$\frac{91}{456}$	$\frac{13}{64}$	
13	1	6	13	10	-5	-14	-9	-2	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{91}{3232}$	$\frac{106}{273}$	$\frac{13}{39}$	
14	1	6	12	5	$-\frac{117}{8}$	$-\frac{45}{2}$	$-\frac{147}{16}$	$-\frac{99}{16}$	$-\frac{2385}{256}$	$-\frac{649}{128}$	$-\frac{381}{256}$	$-\frac{15}{64}$	$-\frac{1}{64}$	$-\frac{2187}{104}$	0	$\frac{243}{104}$	
15	1	6	47	15	$-\frac{261}{16}$	$-\frac{87}{4}$	$-\frac{375}{64}$	$-\frac{531}{64}$	$-\frac{555}{64}$	$-\frac{233}{9}$	$-\frac{3}{4}$	0	0	$-\frac{1944}{91}$	$-\frac{90}{91}$	$-\frac{27}{13}$	
16	1	6	$\frac{23}{2}$	$\frac{5}{2}$	$-\frac{16}{287}$	$-\frac{83}{4}$	$-\frac{64}{19}$	$-\frac{10}{8}$	$-\frac{64}{10}$	$-\frac{9}{16}$	$-\frac{4}{4}$	0	0	$-\frac{1944}{91}$	$-\frac{181}{91}$	$-\frac{27}{13}$	
17	1	6	$\frac{45}{4}$	$\frac{2}{4}$	$-\frac{39}{2}$	$-\frac{39}{2}$	$-\frac{5}{4}$	$-\frac{45}{4}$	$-\frac{16}{6}$	$-\frac{4}{1}$	0	0	0	$-\frac{1944}{91}$	$-\frac{91}{272}$	$-\frac{13}{40}$	
18	1	6	11	0	-21	-18	5	12	4	0	0	0	0	$-\frac{91}{1952}$	$-\frac{360}{91}$	$-\frac{56}{13}$	
19	1	6	$\frac{39}{4}$	$-\frac{25}{4}$	$-\frac{477}{16}$	$-\frac{63}{4}$	$\frac{1329}{64}$	$\frac{1611}{64}$	$-\frac{499}{64}$	$-\frac{165}{32}$	$-\frac{21}{16}$	$-\frac{1}{8}$	$-\frac{1}{8}$	$-\frac{2187}{91}$	$-\frac{810}{91}$	0	
20	1	6	$\frac{19}{2}$	$-\frac{15}{2}$	$-\frac{495}{8}$	$-\frac{51}{4}$	$-\frac{51}{8}$	$-\frac{189}{8}$	$-\frac{64}{21}$	$-\frac{84}{15}$	$-\frac{4}{2}$	0	0	$-\frac{1944}{91}$	$-\frac{909}{91}$	$-\frac{27}{13}$	
21	1	6	$\frac{37}{4}$	$-\frac{35}{4}$	$-\frac{32}{4}$	$-\frac{19}{2}$	$\frac{121}{4}$	$\frac{85}{4}$	$-\frac{13}{2}$	-9	-2	0	0	$-\frac{1944}{91}$	$-\frac{1000}{91}$	$-\frac{144}{13}$	
22	1	6	9	-10	-33	-6	35	18	-12	-8	0	0	0	$-\frac{288}{13}$	$-\frac{152}{13}$	$-\frac{184}{13}$	
23	1	6	$\frac{15}{2}$	$-\frac{35}{2}$	$-\frac{639}{16}$	$-\frac{45}{4}$	$\frac{507}{4}$	$\frac{45}{4}$	$-\frac{639}{16}$	$-\frac{35}{2}$	$\frac{15}{2}$	6	1	0	$-\frac{243}{13}$	$-\frac{243}{13}$	$-\frac{13}{13}$
24	1	6	$\frac{29}{4}$	$-\frac{75}{4}$	$-\frac{81}{2}$	$\frac{33}{2}$	$\frac{273}{4}$	$\frac{2}{4}$	-48	-10	12	4	0	$-\frac{1944}{91}$	$-\frac{1728}{91}$	$-\frac{1080}{13}$	
25	1	6	7	-20	-41	22	73	-8	-56	0	16	0	0	$-\frac{2592}{91}$	$-\frac{1576}{91}$	$-\frac{504}{13}$	
26	1	6	$\frac{21}{4}$	$-\frac{115}{4}$	$-\frac{45}{2}$	$\frac{117}{2}$	$\frac{429}{4}$	$-\frac{279}{4}$	$-\frac{225}{2}$	50	48	-12	-8	$-\frac{17496}{91}$	$-\frac{1944}{91}$	$-\frac{7776}{13}$	
27	1	6	5	-30	-45	66	111	-90	-120	80	48	-32	0	$-\frac{91}{7776}$	$-\frac{360}{91}$	$-\frac{4104}{13}$	
28	1	6	3	-40	-45	126	141	-252	-180	320	48	-192	64	69984	12312	99144	
29	0	0	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{5}{4}$	$\frac{45}{16}$	$\frac{15}{4}$	$\frac{105}{32}$	$\frac{63}{32}$	$\frac{105}{128}$	$\frac{15}{64}$	$\frac{45}{1024}$	$\frac{5}{1024}$	$\frac{1}{4096}$	$\frac{33291}{5824}$	$\frac{909}{1456}$	$-\frac{513}{832}$	
30	0	0	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{5}{4}$	$\frac{11}{4}$	$\frac{7}{4}$	$\frac{32}{49}$	$\frac{32}{49}$	$\frac{128}{35}$	$\frac{64}{1}$	$\frac{17}{1024}$	$\frac{1}{1024}$	0	$\frac{4617}{728}$	$\frac{485}{64}$	$-\frac{9}{13}$	
31	0	0	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{5}{4}$	$\frac{43}{4}$	$\frac{13}{4}$	$\frac{155}{64}$	$\frac{32}{64}$	$\frac{64}{85}$	$\frac{8}{7}$	$\frac{1}{1024}$	$\frac{1}{1024}$	0	$\frac{728}{4923}$	$\frac{728}{64}$	$-\frac{13}{77}$	
32	0	0	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{5}{4}$	$\frac{21}{8}$	$\frac{3}{4}$	$\frac{129}{64}$	$\frac{64}{64}$	$\frac{11}{64}$	$\frac{128}{1}$	$\frac{256}{64}$	0	0	$\frac{91}{638}$	$\frac{87}{64}$	$-\frac{104}{10}$	
33	0	0	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{5}{4}$	$\frac{41}{16}$	$\frac{11}{4}$	$\frac{13}{8}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{16}$	0	0	0	0	$\frac{91}{648}$	$\frac{209}{273}$	$-\frac{31}{39}$	
34	0	0	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{5}{4}$	$\frac{16}{2}$	$\frac{5}{2}$	$\frac{8}{4}$	$\frac{5}{4}$	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{91}{648}$	$\frac{72}{72}$	$-\frac{32}{39}$	
35	0	0	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{5}{4}$	$\frac{9}{4}$	$\frac{3}{2}$	$-\frac{21}{32}$	$-\frac{63}{32}$	$-\frac{105}{64}$	$-\frac{3}{4}$	$-\frac{207}{1024}$	$-\frac{31}{1024}$	$-\frac{1}{512}$	$\frac{4131}{364}$	$\frac{729}{728}$	$-\frac{135}{104}$	
36	0	0	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{5}{4}$	$\frac{2}{2}$	$\frac{2}{2}$	$-\frac{7}{4}$	$-\frac{4}{4}$	$-\frac{5}{4}$	0	0	0	0	$\frac{648}{243}$	$\frac{272}{90}$	$-\frac{40}{39}$	
37	0	0	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{5}{4}$	$\frac{27}{16}$	$-\frac{3}{4}$	$-\frac{213}{64}$	$-\frac{135}{64}$	$\frac{183}{256}$	$\frac{183}{128}$	$\frac{189}{256}$	$\frac{11}{64}$	$\frac{1}{64}$	$\frac{243}{728}$	$\frac{273}{88}$	$-\frac{39}{104}$	
38	0	0	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{5}{4}$	$\frac{3}{2}$	$-\frac{3}{2}$	$-\frac{15}{4}$	$-\frac{3}{4}$	$\frac{2}{2}$	1	0	0	0	$\frac{91}{91}$	$\frac{88}{91}$	$-\frac{16}{13}$	
39	0	0	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{5}{4}$	$\frac{9}{8}$	-3	$-\frac{303}{64}$	$\frac{99}{64}$	$\frac{309}{64}$	$\frac{69}{64}$	$-\frac{45}{32}$	$-\frac{13}{16}$	$-\frac{1}{8}$	$-\frac{243}{91}$	$\frac{99}{91}$	$-\frac{27}{13}$	
40	0	0	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{5}{4}$	$\frac{8}{4}$	1	$-\frac{19}{4}$	$\frac{64}{13}$	$\frac{11}{4}$	$-\frac{1}{2}$	-2	0	0	$\frac{91}{72}$	$\frac{64}{91}$	$-\frac{40}{13}$	
41	0	0	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{5}{4}$	$\frac{9}{16}$	$-\frac{21}{4}$	$-\frac{39}{16}$	$\frac{9}{16}$	$\frac{129}{16}$	$-\frac{15}{2}$	$-\frac{9}{2}$	2	1	$\frac{91}{1944}$	$\frac{87}{152}$	$-\frac{837}{13}$	
42	0	0	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{5}{4}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$-\frac{2}{4}$	$-\frac{19}{4}$	$-\frac{41}{4}$	$\frac{8}{15}$	-10	-4	4	0	$\frac{91}{648}$	$-\frac{91}{152}$	$-\frac{13}{156}$	
43	0	0	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{5}{4}$	0	$-\frac{15}{4}$	$-\frac{15}{4}$	$-\frac{81}{4}$	$\frac{15}{2}$	-30	0	20	-8	$-\frac{9720}{91}$	$-\frac{1584}{91}$	$-\frac{11880}{13}$	
44	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{16}$	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{7}{16}$	$\frac{7}{16}$	$\frac{35}{256}$	$\frac{7}{55}$	$\frac{7}{256}$	$\frac{1}{256}$	$\frac{1}{4096}$	$-\frac{3645}{5824}$	$-\frac{61}{1456}$	$-\frac{63}{832}$	
45	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{16}$	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{16}{27}$	$\frac{16}{25}$	$\frac{64}{55}$	$\frac{128}{9}$	$\frac{64}{13}$	$\frac{1}{1024}$	0	$-\frac{153}{728}$	$-\frac{27}{728}$	$-\frac{5}{104}$	
46	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{16}$	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{13}{32}$	$\frac{11}{32}$	$\frac{64}{256}$	$\frac{128}{128}$	$\frac{1}{256}$	0	0	$-\frac{181}{728}$	$-\frac{3}{91}$	$-\frac{104}{104}$	

47	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{16}$	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{25}{64}$	$\frac{19}{64}$	$\frac{7}{64}$	$\frac{1}{64}$	0	0	0	$-\frac{10}{91}$	$-\frac{8}{273}$	$\frac{1}{39}$	
48	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{16}$	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{1}{32}$	$\frac{1}{64}$	$\frac{1}{64}$	0	0	0	0	0	$-\frac{1}{39}$	$\frac{1}{39}$	$\frac{1}{39}$
49	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{16}$	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{19}{64}$	$\frac{1}{64}$	$-\frac{165}{256}$	$-\frac{31}{128}$	$-\frac{107}{1024}$	$-\frac{23}{1024}$	$-\frac{1}{512}$	$\frac{891}{728}$	$\frac{80}{728}$	$-\frac{52}{728}$	
50	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{16}$	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{1}{64}$	$\frac{1}{64}$	$-\frac{5}{119}$	$-\frac{8}{128}$	0	0	0	$\frac{91}{273}$	$\frac{1}{273}$	$\frac{39}{37}$	
51	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{16}$	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{1}{32}$	$-\frac{32}{256}$	$-\frac{16}{128}$	$-\frac{5}{256}$	$\frac{61}{256}$	$\frac{7}{64}$	$\frac{1}{64}$	$\frac{91}{728}$	$-\frac{91}{3}$	$\frac{104}{3}$	
52	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{16}$	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{1}{8}$	$-\frac{2}{23}$	$-\frac{16}{23}$	$\frac{4}{61}$	$\frac{11}{4}$	$-\frac{5}{0}$	$-\frac{1}{8}$	$-\frac{91}{243}$	$\frac{91}{8}$	$\frac{13}{90}$	
53	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{16}$	$\frac{1}{4}$	0	$-\frac{64}{7}$	$-\frac{64}{5}$	$\frac{64}{32}$	$\frac{32}{1}$	$-\frac{16}{8}$	$-\frac{91}{72}$	$\frac{91}{27}$	$\frac{13}{77}$		
54	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{16}$	$\frac{1}{4}$	0	$-\frac{8}{5}$	$-\frac{7}{16}$	$\frac{8}{8}$	$\frac{4}{4}$	$-\frac{2}{2}$	$-\frac{91}{1296}$	$\frac{91}{179}$	$\frac{13}{1413}$		
55	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{16}$	$\frac{1}{4}$	0	$-\frac{4}{2}$	$\frac{16}{256}$	$\frac{2}{128}$	$\frac{2}{1024}$	$\frac{3}{1024}$	$\frac{1}{4096}$	$\frac{91}{832}$	$\frac{91}{298}$	$\frac{13}{832}$	
56	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{64}$	$\frac{3}{64}$	$\frac{128}{256}$	$\frac{32}{128}$	$\frac{1024}{9}$	$\frac{1024}{1024}$	0	$-\frac{832}{125}$	$-\frac{298}{728}$	$\frac{52}{728}$	
57	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{64}$	$\frac{3}{64}$	$\frac{128}{13}$	$\frac{32}{3}$	$\frac{1024}{1}$	$\frac{1024}{0}$	0	$-\frac{101}{728}$	$-\frac{728}{1}$	$\frac{52}{312}$	
58	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{64}$	$\frac{3}{64}$	$\frac{3}{3}$	$\frac{1}{64}$	0	0	0	$-\frac{10}{91}$	$-\frac{273}{1}$	0	
59	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{64}$	$\frac{3}{64}$	$\frac{128}{3}$	$-\frac{32}{1}$	$-\frac{39}{1024}$	$-\frac{15}{1024}$	$-\frac{1}{512}$	$\frac{91}{11}$	$\frac{728}{1}$	$-\frac{5}{104}$	
60	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{64}$	$\frac{3}{64}$	$\frac{64}{13}$	$-\frac{3}{64}$	$-\frac{32}{3}$	0	0	$\frac{91}{243}$	$-\frac{273}{1}$	$-\frac{39}{77}$	
61	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{64}$	$\frac{3}{64}$	$-\frac{256}{128}$	$-\frac{128}{1}$	$-\frac{256}{256}$	$\frac{64}{64}$	$\frac{64}{64}$	$\frac{728}{8}$	$-\frac{91}{104}$	$-\frac{104}{10}$	
62	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{64}$	$\frac{3}{64}$	$-\frac{64}{3}$	$-\frac{64}{11}$	0	$\frac{16}{3}$	0	$\frac{91}{171}$	$-\frac{19}{91}$	$\frac{13}{167}$	
63	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{64}$	$\frac{3}{64}$	$-\frac{64}{3}$	$-\frac{64}{32}$	$\frac{3}{16}$	$\frac{3}{16}$	$-\frac{1}{8}$	$-\frac{91}{197}$	$-\frac{91}{1456}$	$\frac{7}{832}$	
64	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{256}{1}$	$\frac{128}{1}$	$\frac{512}{5}$	$\frac{512}{1024}$	$\frac{4096}{0}$	$-\frac{5824}{3}$	$-\frac{1456}{2184}$	$\frac{832}{312}$	
65	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{256}{1}$	$\frac{128}{1}$	$\frac{1024}{1}$	$\frac{1024}{0}$	0	$-\frac{91}{104}$	0	$\frac{312}{312}$	
66	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{256}{1}$	$\frac{128}{1}$	$\frac{256}{1}$	0	0	$-\frac{104}{19}$	$\frac{1}{728}$	$\frac{312}{1}$	
67	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{256}{1}$	$\frac{128}{1}$	$-\frac{1024}{1}$	$-\frac{7}{1024}$	$-\frac{1}{512}$	$\frac{728}{3}$	$\frac{13}{31}$	$-\frac{312}{31}$	
68	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{256}{1}$	$\frac{128}{1}$	$-\frac{256}{1}$	$-\frac{1}{1024}$	0	$\frac{728}{3}$	$\frac{273}{2}$	$-\frac{104}{157}$	
69	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{256}{1}$	$\frac{128}{1}$	$-\frac{256}{3}$	$-\frac{1}{64}$	$\frac{1}{64}$	$\frac{179}{5}$	$\frac{91}{2}$	$-\frac{104}{19}$	
70	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1024}{1}$	$\frac{1024}{1}$	$\frac{4096}{0}$	$-\frac{5824}{3}$	$-\frac{4368}{1}$	$-\frac{2496}{1}$	
71	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1024}{1}$	$\frac{1024}{1}$	0	$-\frac{728}{11}$	$-\frac{2184}{5}$	$\frac{78}{312}$	
72	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1024}{1}$	$\frac{1024}{1}$	$-\frac{1}{512}$	$-\frac{364}{17}$	$-\frac{2184}{5}$	$\frac{55}{312}$	
73	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1024}{1}$	$\frac{1024}{1}$	$-\frac{1}{512}$	$-\frac{364}{17}$	$-\frac{2184}{5}$	$\frac{55}{312}$	
74	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{4096}{4096}$	$\frac{5824}{5824}$	$\frac{4368}{4368}$	$-\frac{832}{832}$	0	0	

Table 2/A

No	b_1	b_2	b_3	b_4	b_5	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_6	a_{12}	c_1	c_2	c_3	c_4	c_6	c_{12}
1	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	-24	0	60	-24	0	0	-8	0	0	512
2	0	0	0	9	0	-24	60	0	-24	0	0	-8	0	0	512	0	0
3	0	1	3	2	0	0	0	-8	0	36	-16	0	0	0	0	-8	512
4	0	2	6	1	0	0	0	8	0	12	-8	0	0	0	0	-8	512
5	0	3	1	6	0	-8	36	0	-16	0	0	0	-8	0	512	0	0
6	0	3	9	0	0	0	0	24	0	-12	0	0	0	8	0	-528	1024
7	0	6	2	3	0	8	12	0	-8	0	0	0	-8	0	512	0	0
8	0	9	3	0	0	24	-12	0	0	0	0	8	-528	0	1024	0	0
9	1	0	0	0	11	0	-16	0	32	4	-8	$-\frac{5}{704}$	$\frac{15}{64}$	$\frac{9}{2816}$	$-\frac{5}{22}$	$-\frac{27}{256}$	$\frac{9}{88}$
10	1	0	0	6	3	-16	36	0	-8	0	0	$-\frac{5}{2816}$	$\frac{9}{256}$	0	0	0	0
11	1	0	1	0	9	0	-15	0	27	9	-9	$-\frac{9}{2816}$	$\frac{27}{256}$	$\frac{9}{2816}$	$-\frac{9}{88}$	$-\frac{27}{256}$	$\frac{9}{88}$
12	1	0	2	0	7	0	-14	0	22	14	-10	$-\frac{1056}{79}$	$\frac{32}{256}$	$\frac{1056}{1}$	$-\frac{33}{88}$	$-\frac{32}{256}$	$\frac{33}{88}$
13	1	1	0	1	9	0	-7	0	23	1	-5	$\frac{2816}{3}$	$-\frac{237}{9}$	$\frac{9}{2816}$	$\frac{79}{88}$	$-\frac{27}{256}$	$\frac{9}{88}$
14	1	1	1	1	7	0	-6	0	18	6	-6	$\frac{176}{1}$	$-\frac{9}{16}$	$-\frac{3}{176}$	$\frac{6}{11}$	$\frac{9}{16}$	$-\frac{6}{11}$
15	1	1	2	1	5	0	-5	0	13	11	-7	$\frac{132}{1}$	$-\frac{1}{4}$	$-\frac{1}{132}$	$\frac{8}{33}$	$\frac{1}{4}$	$-\frac{8}{33}$

16	1	2	0	2	7	0	2	0	14	-2	-2	$-\frac{25}{352}$	$\frac{75}{32}$	$-\frac{63}{352}$	$-\frac{25}{11}$	$\frac{189}{32}$	$-\frac{63}{11}$
17	1	2	1	2	5	0	3	0	9	3	-3	$-\frac{3}{44}$	$\frac{9}{4}$	$-\frac{24}{44}$	$-\frac{24}{11}$	$-\frac{9}{4}$	$\frac{24}{11}$
18	1	2	2	2	3	0	4	0	4	8	-4	$-\frac{2}{33}$	$\frac{2}{2}$	$-\frac{64}{33}$	$-\frac{64}{11}$	$-\frac{2}{2}$	$\frac{64}{11}$
19	1	3	0	3	5	0	11	0	5	-5	1	$-\frac{22}{33}$	$\frac{3}{2}$	$-\frac{45}{33}$	$-\frac{16}{11}$	$-\frac{135}{2}$	$\frac{720}{11}$
20	1	3	2	3	1	0	13	0	-5	5	-1	$\frac{16}{33}$	-16	$-\frac{16}{33}$	$\frac{512}{11}$	$\frac{2}{2}$	$-\frac{512}{11}$
21	1	4	0	4	3	0	20	0	-4	-8	4	$\frac{4}{48}$	-12	$-\frac{180}{11}$	$\frac{33}{128}$	16	$-\frac{33}{5760}$
22	1	4	1	4	1	0	21	0	-9	-3	3	$\frac{11}{40}$	-144	$-\frac{48}{11}$	$\frac{1536}{11}$	144	$-\frac{11}{1536}$
23	1	5	0	5	1	0	29	0	-13	-11	7	$\frac{110}{400}$	-1200	$\frac{110}{1008}$	$\frac{12800}{11}$	-3024	$\frac{32256}{11}$
24	1	6	2	0	3	16	-12	0	8	0	0	$-\frac{11}{2}$	$\frac{65}{2}$	0	-32	0	0
25	2	0	0	3	6	-8	12	0	8	0	0	$-\frac{1}{32}$	$\frac{32}{32}$	0	0	0	0
26	2	3	1	0	6	8	-12	0	16	0	0	$\frac{1}{32}$	$-\frac{65}{32}$	0	2	0	0
27	3	0	0	0	9	0	-12	0	24	0	0	$-\frac{1}{256}$	$\frac{33}{256}$	0	$-\frac{1}{8}$	0	0
28	3	0	0	2	1	0	0	-16	0	36	-8	0	0	$-\frac{1}{2}$	0	$\frac{1}{2}$	0
29	3	0	1	0	7	0	-11	0	19	5	-1	$-\frac{19}{8448}$	$\frac{19}{256}$	$\frac{19}{8448}$	$-\frac{19}{264}$	$-\frac{19}{256}$	$\frac{19}{264}$
30	3	0	2	0	5	0	-10	0	14	10	-2	$-\frac{1}{1056}$	$\frac{33}{1056}$	$\frac{1}{1056}$	$-\frac{1}{33}$	$-\frac{1}{171}$	$\frac{32}{33}$
31	3	1	0	1	7	0	-3	0	15	-3	3	$\frac{2816}{2816}$	$-\frac{93}{256}$	$\frac{2816}{88}$	$\frac{10}{5}$	$-\frac{256}{88}$	$\frac{10}{88}$
32	3	1	1	1	5	0	-2	0	10	2	2	$\frac{528}{1}$	$-\frac{16}{1}$	$-\frac{528}{33}$	$\frac{33}{8}$	$\frac{16}{1}$	$-\frac{33}{8}$
33	3	1	2	1	3	0	-1	0	5	7	1	$\frac{132}{1}$	$-\frac{4}{4}$	$-\frac{132}{33}$	$\frac{33}{4}$	$\frac{4}{4}$	$-\frac{33}{8}$
34	3	2	0	2	5	0	6	0	6	-6	6	$-\frac{1}{352}$	$\frac{32}{32}$	$-\frac{352}{1}$	$-\frac{11}{32}$	$\frac{261}{32}$	$-\frac{87}{11}$
35	3	2	1	2	3	0	7	0	1	-1	5	$-\frac{132}{1}$	$\frac{4}{4}$	$\frac{132}{33}$	$-\frac{8}{33}$	$-\frac{4}{64}$	$\frac{33}{64}$
36	3	2	2	2	1	0	8	0	-4	4	4	$-\frac{2}{33}$	$\frac{2}{2}$	$\frac{33}{33}$	$-\frac{2}{33}$	$-\frac{2}{33}$	$\frac{33}{33}$
37	3	2	6	0	1	0	0	16	0	-12	8	0	0	$-\frac{1}{2}$	0	$\frac{65}{2}$	-32
38	3	3	0	3	3	0	15	0	-3	-9	9	$-\frac{1}{22}$	$\frac{3}{2}$	$\frac{45}{22}$	$-\frac{16}{11}$	$-\frac{135}{2}$	$\frac{720}{11}$
39	3	3	1	3	1	0	16	0	-8	-4	8	$-\frac{16}{33}$	16	$\frac{16}{33}$	$-\frac{512}{33}$	-16	$\frac{512}{33}$
40	3	4	0	4	1	0	24	0	-12	-12	12	-4	132	-12	-128	-396	-384
41	5	0	0	0	7	0	-8	0	16	-4	8	$-\frac{7}{4224}$	$\frac{7}{128}$	$-\frac{19}{8448}$	$-\frac{7}{132}$	$\frac{19}{256}$	$-\frac{19}{264}$
42	5	0	1	0	5	0	-7	0	11	1	7	$-\frac{1}{768}$	$\frac{11}{256}$	$\frac{1}{768}$	$-\frac{24}{256}$	$-\frac{1}{24}$	$\frac{1}{24}$
43	5	0	2	0	3	0	-6	0	6	6	6	$-\frac{1056}{13}$	$\frac{32}{13}$	$\frac{1056}{251}$	$-\frac{33}{13}$	$-\frac{32}{251}$	$\frac{33}{251}$
44	5	1	0	1	5	0	1	0	7	-7	11	$\frac{8448}{8448}$	$-\frac{256}{1}$	$\frac{8448}{264}$	$\frac{2}{256}$	$-\frac{256}{264}$	$\frac{2}{264}$
45	5	1	1	1	3	0	2	0	2	-2	10	$\frac{528}{1}$	$-\frac{16}{1}$	$-\frac{528}{33}$	$\frac{33}{8}$	$\frac{16}{1}$	$-\frac{33}{8}$
46	5	1	2	1	1	0	3	0	-3	3	9	$\frac{132}{5}$	$-\frac{4}{5}$	$-\frac{132}{269}$	$\frac{33}{5}$	$\frac{4}{269}$	$-\frac{269}{33}$
47	5	2	0	2	3	0	10	0	-2	-10	14	$\frac{1056}{7}$	$\frac{32}{7}$	$\frac{1056}{33}$	$\frac{33}{7}$	$\frac{32}{7}$	$-\frac{33}{56}$
48	5	2	1	2	1	0	11	0	-7	-5	13	$\frac{132}{66}$	$-\frac{4}{2}$	$\frac{132}{103}$	$\frac{33}{464}$	$-\frac{4}{103}$	$\frac{1648}{33}$
49	5	3	0	3	1	0	19	0	-11	-13	17	0	0	$-\frac{1}{66}$	0	$\frac{1}{2}$	0
50	6	0	0	1	2	0	0	-8	0	12	8	0	0	$-\frac{1}{32}$	0	$\frac{15}{32}$	$-\frac{4}{44}$
51	7	0	0	0	5	0	-4	0	8	-8	16	$-\frac{1}{2816}$	$\frac{3}{256}$	$-\frac{1408}{1}$	$-\frac{1}{88}$	$\frac{128}{1}$	$-\frac{5}{1}$
52	7	0	1	0	3	0	-3	0	3	-3	15	$-\frac{1}{2816}$	$\frac{3}{256}$	$\frac{2816}{1}$	$-\frac{1}{88}$	$-\frac{3}{256}$	$\frac{1}{88}$
53	7	0	2	0	1	0	-2	0	-2	2	14	$-\frac{1}{1506}$	$\frac{1}{32}$	$\frac{1506}{89}$	$-\frac{1}{33}$	$-\frac{1}{267}$	$\frac{1}{33}$
54	7	1	0	1	3	0	5	0	-1	-11	19	$-\frac{1}{2816}$	$\frac{3}{256}$	$\frac{2816}{1}$	$-\frac{1}{88}$	$-\frac{1}{256}$	$\frac{1}{88}$
55	7	1	1	1	1	0	6	0	-6	-6	18	$-\frac{176}{1}$	$\frac{16}{3}$	$\frac{176}{71}$	$-\frac{11}{1}$	$-\frac{16}{213}$	$\frac{11}{71}$
56	7	2	0	2	1	0	14	0	-10	-14	22	$-\frac{17}{352}$	$\frac{51}{32}$	$-\frac{352}{11}$	$-\frac{11}{32}$	$\frac{32}{32}$	$\frac{11}{11}$
57	9	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	-12	24	0	0	$-\frac{1}{256}$	0	$\frac{33}{256}$	$-\frac{1}{8}$
58	9	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	-5	-7	23	$\frac{5}{8448}$	$-\frac{5}{256}$	$-\frac{8448}{73}$	$\frac{5}{264}$	$\frac{256}{73}$	$-\frac{264}{88}$
59	9	1	0	1	1	0	9	0	-9	-15	27	$\frac{2816}{5}$	$-\frac{256}{256}$	$\frac{2816}{88}$	$-\frac{256}{256}$	$-\frac{256}{88}$	$\frac{88}{7}$
60	11	0	0	0	1	0	4	0	-8	-16	32	$-\frac{1}{8448}$	$\frac{3}{256}$	$-\frac{2112}{1}$	$-\frac{1}{264}$	$\frac{64}{64}$	$-\frac{66}{66}$

47	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{32}$	$\frac{7}{64}$	$\frac{3}{128}$	$-\frac{55}{256}$	$-\frac{1}{8}$	$\frac{21}{256}$	$\frac{5}{64}$	$\frac{1}{64}$	$-\frac{4795}{19008}$	$\frac{61}{2112}$	$\frac{269}{9504}$	$\frac{211}{1056}$
48	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{32}$	$\frac{7}{64}$	$\frac{1}{64}$	$-\frac{15}{64}$	$-\frac{7}{64}$	$\frac{1}{8}$	$\frac{1}{16}$	0	$-\frac{7637}{2376}$	$-\frac{5}{33}$	$\frac{1195}{1188}$	$\frac{637}{264}$
49	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{32}$	$\frac{7}{64}$	$-\frac{3}{64}$	$-\frac{25}{64}$	$\frac{1}{64}$	$\frac{15}{32}$	$-\frac{1}{16}$	$-\frac{1}{8}$	$-\frac{31969}{1188}$	$-\frac{421}{264}$	$\frac{5243}{594}$	$\frac{5311}{264}$
50	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{64}$	$\frac{3}{64}$	$\frac{9}{256}$	$\frac{1}{128}$	$-\frac{1}{288}$	0	$\frac{1}{288}$	0	0	0	0
51	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{128}$	$\frac{5}{256}$	$\frac{5}{256}$	$\frac{512}{5}$	$\frac{5}{2048}$	$\frac{1}{4096}$	$\frac{193}{12672}$	$-\frac{5}{2816}$	$\frac{5}{12672}$	$-\frac{5}{352}$
52	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{128}$	$\frac{5}{256}$	$\frac{512}{9}$	$\frac{1024}{5}$	$\frac{1}{1024}$	0	$\frac{397}{25344}$	$-\frac{1}{2816}$	$-\frac{1}{355}$	$-\frac{352}{131}$
53	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{128}$	$\frac{5}{256}$	$\frac{64}{512}$	$\frac{1}{256}$	0	0	$\frac{2987}{57024}$	$\frac{1}{2112}$	$-\frac{1}{28512}$	$-\frac{3168}{5}$
54	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{128}$	$\frac{5}{256}$	$\frac{1}{512}$	$-\frac{17}{1024}$	$-\frac{11}{1024}$	$-\frac{1}{512}$	$\frac{485}{25344}$	$-\frac{1}{2816}$	$-\frac{1}{59}$	$-\frac{352}{91}$
55	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{128}$	$\frac{5}{256}$	0	$-\frac{256}{5}$	$-\frac{128}{1}$	0	$\frac{731}{2112}$	$\frac{13}{704}$	$-\frac{528}{3097}$	$-\frac{352}{779}$
56	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{128}$	$\frac{5}{256}$	$-\frac{1}{64}$	$-\frac{11}{256}$	$\frac{64}{3}$	$\frac{1}{64}$	$\frac{18767}{6336}$	$\frac{704}{704}$	$-\frac{3097}{3168}$	$-\frac{352}{52}$
57	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{512}$	$\frac{1024}{3}$	$\frac{2048}{3}$	$\frac{1}{4096}$	0	0	$\frac{2304}{2831}$	0
58	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{512}{1}$	$\frac{1024}{3}$	$\frac{2048}{3}$	0	$-\frac{8375}{228096}$	$-\frac{19}{8448}$	$\frac{228096}{2743}$	$\frac{1584}{43}$
59	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{512}$	$\frac{1024}{3}$	$-\frac{1024}{3}$	$-\frac{1}{512}$	$-\frac{8287}{25344}$	$-\frac{57}{2816}$	$\frac{25344}{683}$	$\frac{176}{43}$
60	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	$\frac{1}{2048}$	$\frac{1}{4096}$	$\frac{2069}{57024}$	$\frac{19}{8448}$	$-\frac{57024}{1584}$	$-\frac{1584}{1584}$